

Derivatives of *cis*- and *trans*-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutanes and the Synthesis of 6,6-Dimethyl-3-oxabicyclo[3,1,1]heptane

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LAH reduction of *cis*-diethyl norpinate gives *cis*-1,3-bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane, whereas Bouveault-Blanc reduction yields the *trans*-isomer. Both the isomeric diols were characterised through the formation of their bis-phenylurethanes ditosylates, dimesylates, bis-hydrogen phthalates and bis-3,5-dinitrobenzotes. *cis*-Diol has been further used for the formation of its bis-benzoyloxy, bis-acetoxy, bis-methoxy and bis-iodo derivatives. *cis*-1,3-bis(Hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane dimethanesulphonate has also been converted into 6,6-dimethyl-3-oxabicyclo[3, 1, 1]heptane.

THE preparation of *trans*-1,3-bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane from *cis*-diethyl norpinate by its reduction with sodium and ethanol has been reported¹ but no derivative has been mentioned. During the course of the present work, it was found that this method resulted in extremely poor yields due to the competing saponification reaction of the ester with NaOEt. By employing the following modifications the reduction of the *cis*-diethyl norpinate, however, gave the improved yield of the *trans*-diol. (i) Use of *n*-butanol in place of ethanol controls the initial vigorous reaction, ensures complete reduction but lessens the saponification effect; (ii) addition of NH₄Cl further avoids the saponification attack of the alkoxide as per the equation,

and (iii) *o*-xylene used as a solvent keeps Na in a finely divided state and also provides inert medium.

Burgstahler and Sticker² have reported the preparation of *cis*-diol by the LAH reduction of *cis*-norpinic acid anhydride without discussing any of the derivatives except the dimesylate. During the present work, the *cis*-diol has been prepared by the LAH reduction of *cis*-diethyl norpinate and purified through column chromatography. Both the isomeric diols have been characterised through the formation of a number of their derivatives.

Dimesylate of *cis*-1,3-bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane on reaction with alkali gives 6,6-dimethyl-3-oxabicyclo[3,1,1]heptane (3a), whereas similar reaction with *trans*-isomer was not attempted due to its insufficient amount. Further

support to the cyclising ability of *cis*-diol is forthcoming by the formation of isonopinone³ and 6,6-dimethyl-3-thiabicyclo[3,1,1]heptane³ (3b) from the dimesylate of the *cis*-diol.

The nmr spectra of the various intermediates obtained during the preparation of *trans*-norpinic acid from the ω -imide of α',α' -dicyano- β,β -dimethylglutaric acid and *cis*-norpinic acid from α -pinene have been discussed for the first time (Table 1).

Experimental

cis-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane (2a): *cis*-Diethyl norpinate (11.4 g, 0.05 mol) in dry ether (125 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred slurry of LAH (1.9 g, 0.05 mol) in anhydrous ether (200 ml). After stirring for 9 h an additional amount of LAH (1.9 g) was added and the mixture stirred for further 10 h. After cautious addition of a saturated aqueous solution of Na₂SO₄ (10 ml) and then anhydrous Na₂SO₄ (25 g), the contents were filtered and the filtrate concentrated. This was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ and the remaining water removed by azeotropic distillation. Evaporation of the solvent followed by fractionation through column chromatography over silica gel using benzene-ethyl acetate (3:1) as eluent gave 2a (4.3 g, 60%) as small white plates, m.p. 61° (lit. 60°).

cis-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane ditoluene-*p*-sulphonate (2b): To ice-cold solution of *cis*-diol (1.44 g, 0.01 mol) in dry pyridine (5 ml) was added with swirling at *p*-tosyl chloride (4.6 g, 0.022 mol). After chilling 0° for 10 h the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight, the contents were then poured over crushed ice and the solid obtained (m.p. 88°) on crystallisation from benzene yielded

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TABLE 1—NMR SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS*

Sl. no.	Compd.	
1.	2, 2-Dimethylcyclobutane-1,1,3,3-tetracarboxylic acid	1.3 (6H, s, CH ₃), 3.3 (2H, s, CH ₂)
2.	<i>trans</i> -Norpinic acid	1.6 (3H, s, CH ₃), 1.72 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.1-2.5 (4H, m, ring H)
3.	Pinic acid	1.0 (3H, s, CH ₃), 1.3 (3H, s, CH ₃), 1.9-2.3 (3H, m, ring CH ₂ and CHCH ₂ COOH), 2.4 (2H, d, CH ₂ COOH), 2.8 (1H, t, CHCOOH), 10.4 (2H, s, COOH)
4.	Hydroxypinic acid	1.2 (3H, s, CH ₃), 1.3 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2-3.0 (4H, m, ring H), 4.5 (1H, d, CHOH)
5.	3-Carboxy-2,2-dimethylcyclobutan-aldehyde	1.1 (3H, s, CH ₃), 1.4 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2-3.0 (4H, m, ring H), 9.8 (1H, s, CHO), 10.6 (1H, s, COOH)
6.	<i>cis</i> -Norpinic acid	0.9 (3H, s, CH ₃), 1.2 (3H, s, CH ₃), 1.8-3.0 (4H, m, ring H)
7.	<i>cis</i> -Diethyl norpinate	1.1-1.4 (12H, m, CH ₂), 2-3.0 (4H, m, ring H), 4.2-4.6 (4H, q, OCH ₂)
8.	2a	1.0 (3H, s, CH ₃), 1.1 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2-2.6 (4H, m, ring H), 3.6 (4H, d, CH ₂ OH)
9.	2b	0.8 (3H, s, ring CH ₃), 1.0 (3H, s, ring CH ₃), 2.4 (6H, s, ArCH ₃), 3.9 (4H, d, CH ₂ O), 7.2 (4H, d, ArH), 7.4 (4H, d, ArH)
10.	2c	1.1 (3H, s, ring CH ₃), 1.2 (3H, s, ring CH ₃), 2-2.6 (4H, m, ring H), 3.0 (6H, s, CH ₃ SO ₂)
11.	2h	1.2 (3H, s, CH ₃), 1.3 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2-2.6 (4H, m, ring H), 4.4-4.5 (4H, d, CH ₂ O), 9.1 (6H, m, ArH)
12.	2j	1.1 (3H, s, CH ₃), 1.15 (3H, s, CH ₃), 4.3 (4H, d, CH ₂ O), 7.6-8.0 (1H, m, ArH)
13.	1a	3.5-3.8 (4H, m, CH ₂ OH)
14.	1e	4.3-4.6 (4H, m, CH ₂ O), 8-8.4 (8H, m, ArH), 11.8 (2H, s, COOH)

*Solvent for compounds : Pyridine (Sl. no. 1), D₂O-TFA (Sl. nos. 2,6), CDCl₃ (Sl. nos. 3, 5, 7, 8, 10, 11, 13, 14) and CDCl₃-TFA (Sl. nos. 4, 9, 12).

(1)

- 1a; R = OH
 b; R = OTs
 c; R = OMs
 d; R = OCONHC₆H₅

(2)

- 2a; R = OH
 b; R = OTs
 c; R = OMs
 d; R = OCH₃
 e; R = OCOCH₃
 f; R = OCOC₆H₅
 g; R = I

- i; R = OCONHC₆H₅

(3)

- 3a; X = O
 b; X = S

2b (2.5 g, 60%), m.p. 92° (Found : C, 58.3 ; H, 6.3. $C_{22}H_{28}O_6S_2$ requires : C, 58.4 ; H, 6.2%).

cis-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane dimethane sulphonate (2c) : It was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) (82%) m.p. 76° (lit. 75-6°).

cis-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane bis-hydrogen phthalate (2j) : The *cis*-diol was heated at 100° with phthalic anhydride (3 g) in pyridine (5 ml) for 1 h. The contents were cooled, treated with excess of dilute sulphuric acid and the precipitated gummy mass was dissolved in chloroform and extracted with 5% aqueous sodium carbonate. The alkaline layer was acidified and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform layer was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), solvent removed and the residue on crystallisation from alcohol (40%), gave 2j (45%), m.p. 162° (Found : C, 65.4 ; H, 5.5. $C_{24}H_{24}O_8$ requires : C, 65.5 ; H, 5.5%)

cis-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane bis-phenylurethane (2i) : A mixture of *cis*-diol (0.72 g) and phenyl isocyanate (1.5 g) was heated at 100° for 3 h and then stored at room temperature for 1 h. The solid so obtained on crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) gave 2i (48%), m.p. 182° (Found : C, 69.0 ; H, 6.9. $C_{22}H_{26}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 69.1 ; H, 6.8%).

cis-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane bis-3',5'-dinitrobenzoate (2h) : To an ice-cold solution of *cis*-diol (0.72 g) in dry pyridine (5 ml), 3,5-dinitrobenzoyl chloride (0.3 g) was added in small lots with shaking and the contents kept at 0° for 2 h. The solution was diluted with water, and the deposited oil was taken up in chloroform and washed with HCl (5%), water, aqueous sodium carbonate (5%) and finally with water. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and recovering chloroform, the solid on crystallisation from benzene gave 2h (45%), m.p. 172° (Found : C, 49.8 ; H, 3.7. $C_{22}H_{20}O_{12}N_4$ requires : C, 49.6 ; H, 3.8%).

cis-1,3-Bis(methoxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane (2d) : *cis*-Ditoluene *p*-sulphonate (2.26 g) was refluxed with KOH (5 g) in methanol (75 ml) for 3h ; solid potassium toluene *p*-sulphonate obtained on cooling was filtered off and methanol removed at pump. The residual product was diluted with water, extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and solvent removed ; the residue on distillation gave 2d (38%), 90°/8 mm (Found : C, 69.7 ; H, 11.4. $C_{10}H_{20}O_2$ requires : C, 69.8 ; H, 11.6%).

6,6 - Dimethyl - 3-oxabicyclo[3.1.1]heptane (3a) : *cis*-Dimethane sulphonate (4.47 g) was refluxed with aqueous KOH (15%, 100 ml). The reaction mixture was steam distilled and the distillate extracted with ether ; the ethereal layer washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and ether recovered, the residue on distillation gave 3a (75%), 60°/7 mm (Found : C, 76.1 ; H, 11.0, $C_8H_{14}O$ requires : C, 76.2 ; H, 11.1%).

cis-1,3-Bis(acetoxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane (2e) : A mixture of *cis*-diol (0.44 g) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. Then the solution was cooled, diluted with water (25 ml) and the ester extracted with chloroform. The chloroform layer was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (5%), water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and solvent recovered ; the residue on distillation gave 2e (53%), 110°/1 mm (Found : C, 63.3 ; H, 8.7. $C_{12}H_{20}O_4$ requires : C, 63.2 ; H, 8.8%).

cis-1,3-Bis(benzoyloxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane (2f) : The *cis*-diol (1.44 g) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was cooled to 0°, benzoyl chloride (3.5 g) was added in small lots with shaking and the contents kept at 0° for 2 h. The solution was diluted with water, the deposited oil taken up in chloroform and then washed with HCl (5%), water, aqueous sodium carbonate (5%) and finally with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and solvent recovered. The oil so obtained, after fractionating through column chromatography over silica gel using benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) (1 : 1) as eluent and distillation gave 2f (45%), 140°/0.1 mm (Found : C, 74.8 ; H, 6.7. $C_{22}H_{24}O_4$ requires : C, 75.0 ; H, 6.8%).

cis-1,3-Bis(iodomethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane (2g) : *cis*-Ditoluene *p*-sulphonate (2.26 g) was refluxed with acetone (150 ml) containing sodium iodide (5 g) for 3 h and the sodium toluene *p*-sulphonate separated on cooling was filtered off and the filtrate diluted with water. The deposited oil was taken up in ether, the ethereal solution was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and ether recovered. The residue on distillation gave 2g (40%), 90°/1 mm (Found : C, 26.3 ; H, 4.0. $C_8H_{14}I_2$ requires : C, 26.4 ; H, 3.9%).

trans-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane (1a) : To *cis*-diethyl norpinate (0.05 mol) and *o*-xylene (50 ml) containing ammonium chloride (0.3 mol) and *n*-butanol (60 ml) was added sodium (0.3 g atom) carefully. Initial vigorous reaction was controlled by external cooling and when subsided, the contents were refluxed in an oil-bath until most of sodium had reacted (6 h). The reaction mixture was cooled and methanol added slowly to destroy excess of sodium ; to hydrolyse the unreacted ester, water (90 ml) was added and refluxed for 1 h. The contents were cooled and steam-distilled to remove *n*-butanol and *o*-xylene ; the residue extracted with ether, dried (Na_2SO_4) and solvent removed. On distilling under reduced pressure, 1a (40%) was obtained at 120°/3 mm (lit. 125-8°/4 mm) (Found : C, 66.9 ; H, 11.2. $C_8H_{16}O_2$ requires : C, 66.7 ; H, 11.2%).

Derivatives of *trans*-diol were prepared by similar procedures as adopted for *cis*-diol.

trans-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane ditoluene-*p*-sulphonate (1b) : It was crystallised from benzene (50%), m.p. 83° (Found : C, 58.6 ; H, 6.1. $C_{22}H_{28}O_6S_2$ requires : C, 58.4 ; H, 6.2%).

trans-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane dimethyl p-sulphonate (1c): It was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) (60.0%), m.p. 69° (Found: C, 39.8; H, 6.5, $C_{10}H_{20}O_6S_2$ requires: C, 40.0; H, 6.7%).

trans-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane bis-phenylurethane (1d): It was crystallised from petroleum-ether (b.p. 40-60°) (50%), m.p. 176° (Found: C, 69.0; H, 6.6, $C_{22}H_{28}O_4N_2$ requires: C, 69.1; H, 6.8%).

trans-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane bis-hydrogen phthalate (1e): It was crystallised

from alcohol (40%), m.p. 162° (Found: C, 65.3, H, 5.4, $C_{24}H_{24}O_8$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.5%).

trans-1,3-Bis(hydroxymethyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclobutane bis-3',5'-dinitrobenzoate (1f): It was crystallised from benzene (60%), m.p. 165° (Found: C, 49.7; H, 3.6, $C_{22}H_{20}O_{12}N_4$ requires: C, 49.6, H, 3.8%).

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